

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

ACRONYMS IN THE SPHERE PROJECT ENVIRONMENT

1	1D	<u>First Dimension in BIM (Concept Design)</u>
2	2D	<u>Second Dimension in BIM (plane)</u>
3	3D	<u>Third Dimension in BIM (volume)</u>
4	3P	<u>3P (Public Private Partnership)</u>
5	4D	<u>Fourth Dimension in BIM (Time, Scheduling, Planning)</u>
5	5D	<u>Fifth Dimension in BIM (Cost, Budget)</u>
6	6D	<u>Sixth Dimension in BIM (Sustainability)</u>
7	7D	<u>Seventh Dimension in BIM (Facilities Management, Life Cycle)</u>
8	8D	<u>Eighth Dimension in BIM (Safety & Security)</u>
9	9D	<u>Ninth Dimension in BIM (Lean Construction)</u>
10	AAT	<u>Art & Architecture Thesaurus</u>
11	AC	<u>Activities Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
12	AC	<u>Alternating Current</u>
13	ACE	<u>Architects Council of Europe</u>
14	ACFM	<u>Associació Catalana de Facility Management</u>
15	ACT	<u>American Council for Technology</u>
16	AD4	<u>Asset Data Dictionary Definition Document (Crossrail Limited)</u>
17	ADM	<u>Activity Definition Model</u>
18	ADMM	<u>Asset Data Management Manual (Highways Agency)</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

19	ADPE	<u>Abiotic Depletion Potential for non-fossil resources</u>
20	ADPF	<u>Abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources</u>
21	ADQ	<u>Actual Digital Questions (from BIM Acronyms Dictionary)</u>
22	AEC	<u>Architecture, Engineering and Construction</u>
23	AECO	<u>Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Owner (or Owner-operated, or Operation)</u>
24	AECOO	<u>Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Owner Operated</u>
25	AES	<u>Advanced Encryption Standard</u>
26	AEV	<u>Alternative Equivalent Value</u>
27	AFK	<u>Away From the Keyboard</u>
28	AGC	<u>Associated General Contractors (USA)</u>
29	AHRI	<u>Air Conditioning, Heating, and Refrigeration Institute</u>
30	AHU	<u>Air Handling Unit</u>
31	AI	<u>Artificial Intelligence</u>
32	AIA	<u>American Institute of Architects</u>
33	AIM	<u>Adoption Impact Map</u>
34	AIM	<u>Asset Information Model/Modelling</u>
35	AIMS	<u>Asset Information Management System (Crossrail Limited)</u>
36	AIO	<u>All-in-On/one</u>
37	AIR	<u>Asset Information Requirements</u>
38	AISBL	<u>Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif</u>
39	ALE	<u>Asset Life Expectancy</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

40	ALM	<u>Asset Lifecycle Management</u>
41	ALM	<u>Application Lifecycle Management</u>
42	AM	<u>Asset Management</u>
43	AMF	<u>Asset Management Framework</u>
44	AMO	<u>Asset Management Office (Highways Agency)</u>
45	AMP	<u>Agreed Maximum Price</u>
46	AMQP	<u>Advanced Message Queuing Protocol</u>
47	AMR	<u>Automatic Meter Reading</u>
48	ANN	<u>Artificial Neural Network</u>
49	ANSI	<u>American National Standards Institute</u>
50	AOB	<u>Any Other Business</u>
51	AP	<u>Acidification Potential</u>
52	APCE	<u>Associació de Promotors i Constructors d'Edificis de Catalunya</u>
53	API	<u>Application Programming Interface</u>
54	APM	<u>Association for Project Management</u>
55	APPs	<u>Applications</u>
56	AQL	<u>Acceptable Quality Level</u>
57	AR	<u>Augmented Reality</u>
58	ARI	<u>Air-Conditioning and Refrigeration Institute</u>
59	ARL	<u>Asset Remaining Life</u>
60	AS	<u>Appraisal of Service</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

61	ASBL	<u>Association Sans But Lucratif</u>
62	ASCII	<u>American Standard Code for Information Interchange</u>
63	ASC	<u>ASCORA</u>
64	ASHRAE	<u>American Society of Heating Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers</u>
65	ASME	<u>American Society of Mechanical Engineers</u>
66	ASP	<u>Application Service Provider</u>
67	ASSOHQE	<u>Association HQE</u>
68	ATTR	<u>Average Time to Repair (see MTTR)</u>
69	Avanti	<u>(UK Government sponsored to assist collaboration)</u>
70	AVG	<u>Average</u>
71	B&ES	<u>Building and Engineering Services Association (formerly, till 2012, known as HVCA). (See BESA)</u>
72	BACS	<u>Building Automation and Control System</u>
73	BAM	<u>BIM Acceptance Model</u>
74	BAS	<u>Building Automation System</u>
75	BASF	<u>Badische Anilin - und SodaFabrik</u>
76	BBSR	<u>Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development</u>
77	BCF	<u>BIM Collaborative Format</u>
78	BCHS	<u>Barcode Housing System</u>
79	bcXML	<u>Building and Construction eXtensible mark-up Language</u>
80	BDS	<u>Building Description System</u>
81	BDT	<u>Building Digital Twin</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

82	BDTA	<u>Building Digital Twin Aggregates</u>
83	BDTAS(S)	<u>Building Digital Twin Association</u>
84	BDTcM	<u>Building Digital Twin Configuration Manager</u>
85	BDTE	<u>Building Digital Twin Environment</u>
86	BDTI	<u>Building Digital Twin Instance</u>
87	BDTIC	<u>Building Digital Twin International Congress</u>
88	BDTM	<u>Building Digital Twin Manager</u>
89	BDTP	<u>BIM Digital Twin Platform</u>
90	BDTP	<u>BIM Digital Twin Prototype</u>
91	BDTsM	<u>Building Digital Twin Simulation Manager</u>
92	BEI	<u>Baseline Emission Inventory (BEI): Quantifies the amount of CO2 emitted due to energy consumption in the territory of the Covenant signatory in the baseline year.</u>
93	BEIF	<u>Built Environment Information Fabric</u>
94	BEIS	<u>Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy</u>
95	BEM	<u>Building Energy Management</u>
96	BEMS	<u>Building Energy Management System</u>
97	BEP	<u>BIM Execution Plan</u>
98	BEP	<u>Building Energy Performance</u>
99	BEP DT	<u>BIM Execution Plan Digital Twin</u>
100	BERR	<u>Business, Enterprise and Regulatory Reform</u>
101	BES	<u>Building Energy Simulation</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

102	BESA	<u>Building Engineering Services Association (See B&ES)</u>
103	BFM	<u>Building Facility Manager</u>
104	BI	<u>Business Insider</u>
105	BI	<u>Business Intelligence</u>
106	BIEM's	<u>Building Indoor Environment Models</u>
107	BIM	<u>Building Information Model</u>
108	BIM	<u>Building Information Modelling</u>
109	BIM	<u>Building Information Management</u>
110	BIM(M)	<u>Building Information Modelling and Management</u>
111	BIPV	<u>Building Integrated Photovoltaic</u>
112	BIS	<u>Business, Innovation and Skills (See BEIS)</u>
113	BLE	<u>Bluetooth Low Energy (Bluetooth LE)</u>
114	BLIS	<u>Building Lifecycle Interoperable Software</u>
115	BLPU	<u>Basic Land and Property Unit</u>
116	BMI	<u>Body Mass Index</u>
117	BMI	<u>Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community</u>
118	BMLVS	<u>Backup Main Low Voltage Switchboard</u>
119	BMS	<u>Building Management System</u>
120	BMS	<u>Battery Management System</u>
121	BMVI	<u>BundesMinisteriums für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur</u>
122	BNB	<u>Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

123	BOM	<u>Bill of Materials</u>
124	BOM	<u>Building Office Manager</u>
125	BOMA	<u>Building Owners and Managers Association</u>
126	BOM's	<u>Building Object Models</u>
127	BOOT	<u>Build-own-operate-transfer (See BOT)</u>
128	BOQ	<u>Bill of Quantities (See BQ)</u>
129	BOT	<u>Building Topology Ontology</u>
130	BOT	<u>Build-Operate Transfer (See BOOT)</u>
131	BPE	<u>Baseline Period Energy</u>
132	BPE	<u>Building Performance Evaluation</u>
133	BPEP	<u>BIM Project Execution Plan</u>
134	BPI	<u>Building Performance Indicator</u>
135	BPIC	<u>Building Project Information Committee</u>
136	BPL	<u>Broadband over Power Lines</u>
137	BPMN	<u>Business Process Model and Notation</u>
138	BPNN	<u>Back-Propagation Neural Network</u>
139	BQ	<u>Bill of Quantities (See BOQ)</u>
140	BQBS	<u>Bill of Quantities (or BQ) Breakdown Structure</u>
141	BRE	<u>Building Research Establishment</u>
142	BREEAM	<u>Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method</u>
143	BRep	<u>Boundary Representation</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

144	BrIM	<u>Bridge Information Model</u>
145	BS	<u>British Standard</u>
146	BSA	<u>Building Smart Alliance</u>
147	BSD	<u>Building Systems Design</u>
148	bSDD	buildingSMART Data Dictionary
149	BSI	<u>British Standards Institute</u>
150	BSI	<u>Building Smart International</u>
151	BSIM	<u>Building Services Information Model (See BIM)</u>
152	BSRIA	<u>Building Services Research and Information Association</u>
153	CA	<u>Contract Administrator</u>
154	CAATEEB	<u>Col·legi de' Aparelladors, Arquitectes Tècnics i Enginyers d'Edificació de Catalunya</u>
155	CAC	<u>Cost of Customer Acquisition</u>
156	CAD	<u>Computer-Aided Design</u>
157	CADD	<u>Computer-Aided Design and Drafting</u>
158	CAE	<u>Computer Aided Engineering</u>
159	CAFm	<u>Computer-Aided Facility Management</u>
160	CAI	<u>Computer Aided inspection</u>
161	CAM	<u>Computer Aided Manufacture</u>
162	CAPex	<u>Capital Expenditure</u>
163	CAPP	<u>Computer-Aided Process Planning</u>
164	CAR	<u>Collection, Assessment and Response</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

165	CASBEE	<u>Comprehensive Assessment System for Building Environmental Efficiency</u>
166	CATIA	<u>Computer Aided Three-dimensional Interactive Application</u>
167	CAV	<u>Caverion</u>
168	CAWS	<u>Common Arrangement of Work Sections</u>
169	CBC	<u>Construction Blockchain Consortium</u>
170	CBP	<u>Capacity Bidding Program</u>
171	CBS	<u>Cost Breakdown Structure</u>
172	CCIP	<u>Contractor Controller Insurance Program</u>
173	CCIR	<u>International Radio Consultative Committee</u>
174	CCMS	<u>Construction Coordination Management Services</u>
175	CCOs	<u>Contract Change Orders</u>
176	CCTA	<u>Central Computer and Telecommunications Agency</u>
177	CCUS	<u>Carbon Capture, Use, and Storage</u>
178	CD	<u>Compact Disc</u>
179	CDBB	<u>Centre for Digital Built Britain</u>
180	CDCL	<u>Compagnie de Construction Luxembourgeoise</u>
181	CDD	<u>Cooling Degree Days</u>
182	CDE	<u>Common Data Environment</u>
183	CDF	<u>Common Data Format</u>
184	CDM	<u>Construction (Design and Management) Regulations</u>
185	CDPA	<u>Copyright, Designs and Patent Act</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

186	CD-ROM	<u>Compact Disc Read-only Memory</u>
187	CE	<u>Constructing Excellence</u>
188	CEAT	<u>Circular Economy Assessment Tool</u>
189	CEAT	<u>Circular Environmental Assessment Toolkit</u>
190	CEC	<u>Commission for Environmental Cooperation</u>
191	CECE	<u>Committee for European Construction Equipment</u>
192	CEDT	<u>Central European Daylight Time</u>
193	CEI	<u>Commission Électrotechnique Internationale</u>
194	CEN	<u>European Committee for Standardisation</u>
195	CENELEC	<u>European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization</u>
196	CEO	<u>Chief Executive Officer</u>
197	CERL	<u>Construction Engineering Research Laboratory (USACE)</u>
198	CERN	<u>Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire</u>
199	CEST	<u>Central European Summer Time</u>
200	CET	<u>Central European Time</u>
201	CEWEP	<u>Confederation of European Waste-to-Energy Plants</u>
202	CFB	<u>Call for Bids</u>
203	CFC	<u>Chlorofluorocarbon</u>
204	CFD	<u>Computational (or Computed) Fluid Dynamics</u>
205	CFR	<u>Central Facilities Repository</u>
206	CFRP	<u>Carbon Fiber Reinforcement Polymer</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

207	C/I	<u>Civils/Infrastructure</u>
208	CI	<u>Continuous Improvement (the same as CIP and CPI)</u>
209	CI's	<u>Configuration Item</u>
210	CIA	<u>Cost Impact Analysis</u>
211	CIAT	<u>Chartered Institute of Architectural Technologists</u>
212	CIB	<u>International Council for Research and Innovation in Building and Construction (Ant. Conseil International du Bâtiment)</u>
213	CIBSE	<u>Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers</u>
214	CIC	<u>Construction Industry Council</u>
215	CIFE	<u>Center for Integrated Facility Engineering (Stanford University)</u>
216	CIM	<u>City Information Modelling</u>
217	CINT	<u>Communication Interval</u>
218	CIOB	<u>The Chartered Institute of Building</u>
219	CIP	<u>Continuous Improvement Process</u>
220	CIR	<u>Contractor's Information Requirements</u>
221	CIS	<u>Construction Information Service</u>
222	CITE	<u>Construction Industry Trading Electronically</u>
223	CityGML	<u>City Geography Markup Language</u>
224	CL	<u>Construction Lean (see Lean Construction)</u>
225	CM	<u>Configuration Management/Manager</u>
226	CM	<u>Construction Manager</u>
227	CMa	<u>Construction Manager Advisor</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

228	CMAA	<u>Construction Management Association of America</u>
229	CMAR	<u>Construction Management At Risk (the same as CMc)</u>
230	CMc	<u>Construction Manager as Constructor (the same as CMAR)</u>
231	CMDB	<u>Configuration Management Database</u>
232	CMM	<u>Capability Maturity Model</u>
233	CMM	<u>Coordinate Measurement Machine</u>
234	CMMS	<u>Computerized Maintenance Management System</u>
235	CMS	<u>Compact Muon Solenoid</u>
236	CMT	<u>Concrete Management Tool</u>
237	CNC	<u>Computerized Numerical Controllers</u>
238	CO	<u>Carbon Monoxide</u>
239	CO	<u>Complexes Table (CPCI Uniclass 2)</u>
240	COAC	<u>Col·legi Oficial d'Arquitectes de Catalunya</u>
241	COBie	<u>Construction Operations Building information Exchange</u>
242	COEIC	<u>Col·legi Oficial d'Enginyers Industrials de Catalunya</u>
243	COINS	<u>Construction Industry Software</u>
244	COM	<u>Component Object Model</u>
245	COME	<u>COMET GESINCO</u>
246	COMS	<u>COMSA</u>
247	COO	<u>Chief Operating Officer</u>
248	COP	<u>Coefficient of Practice</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

249	COP	<u>Coefficient of Performance</u>
250	COS	<u>Conditions of Satisfaction</u>
251	CPaaS	<u>Communications Platform as a Service</u>
252	CPC	<u>Central Product Classification</u>
253	CPD	<u>Continuing Professional Development</u>
254	CPET	<u>Cardiopulmonary Exercise Testing</u>
255	CPI	<u>Coordinated Project Information</u>
256	CPI	<u>Continuous Process Improvement (the same as CIP)</u>
257	CPIC	<u>Construction Project Information Committee (also named CPI)</u>
258	CPIX	<u>Construction Project Information Xchange</u>
259	CPMS	<u>Capital Planning and Management System</u>
260	CPMS	<u>Construction Project Management System</u>
261	CPR	<u>Construction Progress Reporting</u>
262	CPS	<u>Cyber Physical Systems</u>
263	CPU	<u>Central Processing Unit</u>
264	CPX	<u>Cardiopulmonary Exercise Testing</u>
265	CR	<u>Clash Rendition</u>
266	CRC	<u>Carbon Reduction Commitment</u>
267	CREE	<u>CREE Rhomberg</u>
268	CRL	<u>Crossrail Limited</u>
269	CRM	<u>Customer Relationship Management</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

270	CRS	<u>Coordinate Reference System</u>
271	CRTI-B	<u>Centre de Ressources des Technologies et de l'Innovation pour le Bâtiment</u>
272	CRU	<u>Components for Re-Use</u>
273	CRUD	<u>Create, Read, Update and Delete</u>
274	CRV	<u>Capitalised Replacement Value</u>
275	CS	<u>Coordinate Systems</u>
276	CSA	<u>Coordination and Support Actions</u>
277	CSC	<u>Computer Sciences Corporation</u>
278	CSCW	<u>Computer Supported Collaborative Working</u>
279	CSG	<u>Constructive Solid Geometry</u>
280	CSI	<u>Construction Specifications Institute</u>
281	CSS	<u>Cascading Style Sheets</u>
282	CSS	<u>Chirp Spread Spectrum</u>
283	CSV	<u>Comma Separated Values</u>
284	CTE	<u>Código Técnico de Edificación (Spain)</u>
285	CURT	<u>Construction Users Roundtable</u>
286	CV-RMSE	<u>Coefficient of Variation of Root-Mean Squared Error</u>
287	D	<u>Deliverable</u>
288	DAA	<u>Digital Analytical Association</u>
289	DAE	<u>Differential Algebraic Equations</u>
290	DAF	<u>Dissolve Air Flotation</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

291	D2RQ	<u>Database to RDF Query</u>
292	DB	<u>Database</u>
293	DB – D&B	<u>Design-Build</u>
294	DB	<u>Documento Básico (Spain)</u>
295	DB	<u>Dry Bulb</u>
296	DBB	<u>Design-Bid-Build</u>
297	DBC	<u>Design Build Contract</u>
298	DBFM	<u>Design-Build-Finance-Maintain</u>
299	DBFO	<u>Design, Build, Finance, Operate</u>
300	DBIA	<u>Design Build Institute of America</u>
301	DBMS	<u>Data Base Management System</u>
302	DBT	<u>Dry Bulb Temperature</u>
303	DC	<u>Direct Current</u>
304	DCE-RPC	<u>Distributed Computing Environment - Remote Procedure Call</u>
305	DCF	<u>Discounted Cash Flow</u>
306	DCLG	<u>Department for Communities and Local Government</u>
307	DCOM	<u>Distributed Component Object Model</u>
308	DCS	<u>Distributed Control System</u>
309	DDBB	<u>Databases</u>
310	DDC	<u>Direct Digital Controller</u>
311	DDS	<u>Data Design System</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

312	DE5	<u>DE5 SERVICES SRL</u>
313	DERMS	<u>Distributed Energy Resources Management Systems</u>
314	DERs	<u>Distributed Energy Resources</u>
315	DFEE	<u>Dwelling Fabric Energy Efficiency</u>
316	DFMA	<u>Design for Manufacturer and Assembly</u>
317	DfT	<u>Department for Transport</u>
318	DGNB	<u>Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen</u>
319	DHW	<u>Domestic Hot Water</u>
320	DID	<u>Direct Inward Dialling</u>
321	DIP	<u>Dual In-line Package</u>
322	DIUS	<u>Department for Innovation, Universities and Skills</u>
323	DL	<u>Description Logic</u>
324	DL	<u>Deadline</u>
325	DL	<u>Deep Learning</u>
326	DLT	<u>Distributed Ledger Technology</u>
327	DMP	<u>Data Management Plan</u>
328	DMS	<u>Document Management System</u>
329	DNA	<u>Deoxyribonucleic acid</u>
330	DoA	<u>Description of Action</u>
331	DOT	<u>Damage Topology Ontology</u>
332	DPB	<u>Discounted Pay-Back</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

333	DPP	<u>Developed Constructor Proposal</u>
334	DR	<u>Demand Response</u>
335	DRC	<u>Depreciated Replacement Cost</u>
336	DRMS	<u>Demand Response Management System</u>
337	DS	<u>Digital Shadow</u>
338	DSM	<u>Demand-Side Management</u>
339	DSM	<u>Design Structure Matrix</u>
340	DSO	<u>Distribution System Operators</u>
341	DSR	<u>Demand-Side Response</u>
342	DSS	<u>Data Security Standard</u>
343	DSS	<u>Decision Support System</u>
344	DT	<u>Digital Twin</u>
345	DTA	<u>Digital Twin Aggregate</u>
346	DTC	<u>Digital Twin Consortium</u>
347	DTcM	<u>Digital Twin Configuration Manager</u>
348	DTE	<u>Digital Twin Environment</u>
349	DThread	<u>Digital Thread</u>
350	DTI	<u>Digital Twin Instance</u>
351	DTI	<u>Digital Twin Institute</u>
352	DTM	<u>Digital Twin Manager</u>
353	DTP	<u>Digital Twin Platform</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

354	DTP	<u>Digital Twin Principles</u>
355	DTP	<u>Digital Twin Prototype</u>
356	DTsM	<u>Digital Twin Simulation Manager</u>
357	DTT	<u>Digital Twin Technologies</u>
358	DTV	<u>Design Transfer View</u>
359	DU	<u>Dumb, Uncommunicative</u>
360	DVD-ROM	<u>Digital Versatile Disc – Read-Only Memory</u>
361	DXF	<u>Drawing eXchange Format</u>
362	DXF	<u>DaTA eXchange Format</u>
363	EA	<u>Empresarios Agrupados</u>
364	EA	<u>Evolutionary Algorithm</u>
365	EAB	<u>External Advisory Board</u>
366	EAI	<u>Empresarios Agrupados Internacional</u>
367	EAM	<u>Enterprise Asset Management</u>
368	eBOM	<u>Engineering Bill of Materials</u>
369	EBRD	<u>European Bank for Reconstruction and Development</u>
370	EBS	<u>European BIM Summit</u>
371	EC	<u>European Commission/Committee</u>
372	ECAS	<u>European Commission Authentication Service</u>
373	ECD	<u>Entorno Común de Datos</u>
374	ECI	<u>European Construction Institute</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

375	ECI	<u>Early Contractor Involvement</u>
376	ECI	<u>Environmental Cost Indicator</u>
377	ECM	<u>Electronic Control Module</u>
378	ECM's	<u>Energy Conservation Measures</u>
379	EcosimPro	<u>EcosimPro</u>
380	ECU	<u>Electronic Control Unit</u>
381	EDCE	<u>Energy Demand Calculation Engine</u>
382	EDI	<u>Electronic Data Interchange</u>
383	EDM	<u>Electronic Distance Measurement</u>
384	EDMS	<u>Electronic Distance Measurement System</u>
385	Ee	<u>Elements Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
386	EE	<u>Energy Efficiency</u>
387	EEA	<u>European Economic Area</u>
388	EEAB	<u>External Expert Advisory Board</u>
389	EEB	<u>Energy Efficient Building</u>
390	EEB	<u>European Environmental Bureau</u>
391	EED	<u>Energy Efficiency Directive</u>
392	EEE	<u>Exported Electrical Energy</u>
393	EEO's	<u>Energy Efficiency Obligations</u>
394	EER	<u>Energy Efficiency Ratio</u>
385	EET	<u>Exported Thermal Energy</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

396	EF	<u>Environmental Footprint</u>
397	EFPA	<u>European Financial Planning Association</u>
398	EFTA	<u>European Free Trade Association</u>
399	EGDI	<u>E-Government Development Index</u>
400	EGS	<u>Enhanced Geothermal Systems</u>
401	EHS	<u>European Home System</u>
402	EHSA	<u>European Home Systems Association</u>
403	EIB	<u>European Installation Bus</u>
404	EIC	<u>European Innovation Council</u>
405	EIF	<u>European Interoperability Framework</u>
406	EIR	<u>Employer's Information Requirements</u>
407	EIR	<u>Exchange Information Requirements</u>
408	EKO	<u>Ekodenge</u>
409	ELCD	<u>European Reference Life Cycle Database</u>
410	ELM	<u>Evidence Log Module</u>
411	ELSC	<u>Enterprise Leadership Steering Committee</u>
412	EMS	<u>Energy Management System</u>
413	EMS	<u>Environment Management System</u>
414	En	<u>Entities Table (CPIC Unicals 2)</u>
415	EN	<u>EuroNorm</u>
416	EnBs	<u>Energy Baseline</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

417	EnMS	<u>Energy Management System</u>
418	EnPi	<u>Energy Performance Indicator</u>
419	ENR	<u>Engineering News Record</u>
420	EOL	<u>End of Life</u>
421	EOTA	<u>European Organisation for Technical Approvals</u>
422	EP	<u>European Parliament</u>
423	EP	<u>Eutrophication potential</u>
424	EPA	<u>Environmental Protection Agency</u>
425	EPBD	<u>Energy Performance of Buildings Directive</u>
426	EPC	<u>Energy Performance Certificate</u>
427	EPC	<u>Energy Performance Coefficient</u>
428	EPC	<u>Energy Performance Contract</u>
429	EPD	<u>Environmental Product Declaration</u>
430	EPPM	<u>Engineering, Project, and Production Management</u>
431	EQM	<u>European Quality Mark</u>
432	ER	<u>Exchange Requirements</u>
433	ER	<u>Exploitable Results</u>
434	ERDC	<u>Engineering Research and Development Center</u>
435	ERP	<u>Enterprise Resource Planning</u>
436	ERs	<u>Expectable Results</u>
437	ESCO	<u>Energy Service Company</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

438	ESEER	<u>European Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio</u>
439	ESPC	<u>Energy Savings Performance Contract</u>
440	ESR	<u>Evaluation Summary Report</u>
441	ESS	<u>Energy Storage Systems</u>
442	ETC	<u>Engineering and Technology Board</u>
443	ETCP	<u>European Construction Technology Platform</u>
444	ETL	<u>Extract, Transform and Load</u>
445	ETPIS	<u>European Technology Platform on Industrial Safety</u>
446	ETSI	<u>European Telecommunication Standards Institute</u>
447	EU	<u>European Union</u>
448	EUI	<u>Energy Use Intensity</u>
449	EUPPD	<u>European Union Public Procurement Directive</u>
450	EUQ	<u>Element Unit Quantity</u>
451	EUR	<u>Element Unit Rate</u>
452	EURECAT	<u>Technological Centre in Catalonia</u>
453	EUT	<u>EURECAT</u>
454	EV	<u>Electric Vehicle</u>
455	EVA	<u>Earned Value Analysis</u>
456	EVO	<u>Efficiency Valuation Organization</u>
457	EWP	<u>Early Works Packages</u>
458	FAIR	<u>Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

459	FAQ	<u>Frequently Asked Questions</u>
460	FAT	<u>Factory Acceptance Test</u>
461	FAT	<u>FeuerwehrAnzeigeTableau</u>
462	FBF	<u>Feuerwehr-BedienFeld</u>
463	FCI	<u>Facilities Condition Index</u>
464	FCI	<u>Function Condition Indexation</u>
465	FDD	<u>Fault Detection and Diagnosis</u>
466	FEA	<u>Finite Element Analysis</u>
467	FEE	<u>Fabric Energy Efficiency</u>
468	FEM	<u>Finite Element Method</u>
469	FET	<u>The field-effect transistor</u>
470	FF&A	<u>Furniture, Fixtures and Accessories</u>
471	FFE or FF&E	<u>Furniture, Fitting (or Fixtures) and Equipment</u>
472	FFL	<u>Finished Floor Level</u>
473	FFNN	<u>Feedforward Neural Network</u>
474	FFP	<u>Fitness for Purpose</u>
475	FIEBDC	<u>Formato de Intercambio Estándar de Bases de Datos para la Construcción</u>
476	FIEC	<u>European Construction Industry Federation</u>
477	FIM	<u>Facilities Information Model</u>
478	FIM	<u>Facility Intelligent Management</u>
479	Flink2Go	<u>Flink2Go</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

480	FM	<u>Facility/ies Management</u>
481	FM	<u>Facility Manager</u>
482	FMA	<u>Facilities Management Association</u>
483	FMI	<u>Facilities Maintenance Indexation</u>
484	FMI	<u>Finnish Meteorological Institute</u>
485	FMI	<u>Functional Mock-up Interface</u>
486	FMP	<u>Forward Maintenance Plans (or programme)</u>
487	FOAF	<u>Friend of a Friend</u>
488	FOG	<u>File Ontology for Geometry formats</u>
489	FRCT	<u>Fiber Reinforced Concrete Tool</u>
490	FRI	<u>Function Re-investment Indexation</u>
491	FRS	<u>Factory Replication</u>
492	FRS	<u>Front Running Simulation</u>
493	FRS	<u>First Run Studies</u>
494	FTI	<u>Fast Track to Innovation</u>
495	FTP	<u>File Transfer Protocol</u>
496	FW	<u>Fresh Water (Use of)</u>
497	GA's	<u>General Arrangement Drawings</u>
498	GA	<u>General Assembly</u>
499	GA	<u>Grant Agreement</u>
500	GaBI	<u>GaBI LCA Database</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

501	GAMA	<u>Gas Appliance Manufacturers Association</u>
502	GBCE	<u>Green Building Council España</u>
503	GBXML	<u>Green Building Extensible Modelling Language</u>
504	GC	<u>General Contractor</u>
505	GCCB	<u>Government Construction Client Group</u>
506	GCS	<u>Government Construction Strategy</u>
507	GD&T	<u>General Dimensioning and Tolerances</u>
508	GDL	<u>Geometric Description Language</u>
509	GDPR	<u>General Data Protection Regulation</u>
510	GEA	<u>Global Energy Assessment</u>
511	GEA	<u>Gross External Area</u>
512	GEOFIT	<u>GEOthermal systems, technologies and tools for energy efficient building retroFITting</u>
513	GFA	<u>Gross Floor Area</u>
514	GHG	<u>Green House Gases</u>
515	GIA	<u>Gross Internal Area</u>
516	GIFA	<u>Gross Internal Floor Area</u>
517	GIGO	<u>Garbage In, Garbage Out</u>
518	GIS	<u>Geographical Information System</u>
519	GML	<u>Geography Markup Language</u>
520	GMP	<u>Guaranteed Maximum Price</u>
521	GMSD	<u>Generative Modular Building System Design</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

522	GMT	<u>Greenwich Mean Time</u>
523	GNSS	<u>Global Navigation Satellite System</u>
524	GOM	<u>Geometry Metadata</u>
525	GP	<u>Gemini Principles</u>
526	GPS	<u>Global Positioning System</u>
527	GRIP	<u>Governance for Railway Investment Projects</u>
528	GRNN	<u>Generalized Regression Neural Network</u>
529	GSA	<u>Government Services Administration (US)</u>
530	GSA	<u>General Services Administration</u>
531	GSL	<u>Government Soft Landings</u>
532	GUI	<u>Graphical User Interface</u>
533	GUID	<u>Globally Unique Identifier</u>
534	GWP	<u>Global Warming Potential</u>
535	H2020	<u>Horizon 2020</u>
536	H&S	<u>Health and safety</u>
537	HA	<u>Highways Agency</u>
538	HADEA	<u>Health and Digital Executive Agency</u>
539	HASL	<u>Height Above Sea Level</u>
540	hBDTA	<u>Horizontal Building Digital Twin Aggregate</u>
541	HBI	<u>Human Building Interfaces</u>
542	HCI	<u>Human-Computer Interaction</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

543	HCOME	<u>Human-Centered Ontology Engineering Methodology</u>
544	HCONE	<u>Human-Centered ONtology Engineering Environment</u>
545	HDD	<u>Heating Degree Days</u>
546	HDR	<u>Hot Dry Rock</u>
547	HERA	<u>Health Emergency Response Authority</u>
548	HIL	<u>Hardware in the Loop</u>
549	HHS	<u>Health and Human Services (US)</u>
550	HMG	<u>Her Majesty's Government</u>
551	HMI	<u>Human Machine Interface</u>
552	HOAI	<u>Honorarordnung für Architekten und Ingenieure</u>
553	HQE	<u>Haute Qualité Environnementale</u>
554	HR	<u>Human Resources</u>
555	HSE	<u>Health and Safety Executive</u>
556	HTM	<u>Hypertext Markup</u>
557	HTM	<u>Human Thermal Model</u>
558	HTMD	<u>Human Thermal Model Description</u>
559	HTML	<u>Hypertext Markup Language</u>
560	HTTP	<u>Hypertext Transfer Protocol</u>
561	HTTPS	<u>HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure</u>
562	HUB	<u>HUB</u>
563	HV	<u>High Voltage</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

564	HVAC	<u>Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning</u>
565	HVM	<u>Home Ventilation Machine</u>
566	HVM	<u>Human Ventilation Model</u>
567	HWD	<u>Hazardous Waste Disposed</u>
568	IA	<u>Innovation Actions</u>
569	laaS	<u>Infrastructure as a Service</u>
570	IAC	<u>Industry Advisory Council</u>
571	IAI	<u>International Alliance for Interoperability</u>
572	IAM	<u>Institute of Asset Management</u>
573	IAQ	<u>Indoor Air Quality</u>
574	IB	<u>Intelligent Building</u>
575	IBACOS	<u>Integrated Building and Construction Solutions</u>
576	IBC	<u>International Building Code</u>
577	IBC	<u>Institute for BIM in Canada</u>
578	IBD	<u>Intelligent Building Data</u>
579	iBIM	<u>Integrated BIM</u>
580	ICAEN	<u>Institut Català d'Energia</u>
581	ICC	<u>International Code Council</u>
582	ICD	<u>Integrated Cycle Design</u>
583	ICD	<u>Intelligent Community Design</u>
584	ICD	<u>Interface Control Documents</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

585	ICE	<u>Institution of Civil Engineers and Innovative Contractor Engagement</u>
586	iCIM	iCIM is a community resource monitoring and management platform that improves sustainability performance (see IESVE)
587	ICIS	<u>International Construction Information Society</u>
588	ICL	<u>Intelligent Communities Lyfecicle</u>
589	ICONDA	<u>International CONstruction Database</u>
590	ICT	<u>Information and Communication Technologies</u>
591	ID	<u>Identification</u>
592	IDABC	<u>Interoperable Delivery of European eGovernment Services to public Administrations, Business and Citizens</u>
593	IDAE	<u>Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía (Spain)</u>
594	IDD	<u>Integrated Design & Delivery</u>
595	IDD	<u>Integrated Digital Delivery</u>
596	IDDS	<u>Integrated Design & Delivery Solutions/Service</u>
597	IDM	<u>Information Delivery Manual</u>
598	IDP	<u>IDP Ingeniería, Medio Ambiente y Arquitectura</u>
599	IDP	<u>Integrated Design Process</u>
600	IDP	<u>Intelligent Design Planning</u>
601	IDS	<u>Integrated Design Solutions</u>
602	IDT	<u>Infrastructure Digital Twins</u>
603	IE	<u>Information Exchange</u>
604	IEC	<u>International Electrotechnical Commission</u>
605	IEEE	<u>Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

606	IEP	<u>Individual Education Plan</u>
607	IEQ	<u>Indoor Environmental Quality</u>
608	IES	<u>Integrated Environmental Solutions</u>
609	iESD_E	<u>Intelligent Energy System Designer</u>
610	IESVE	<u>IES Virtual Environment</u>
611	IFB	<u>Invitation for Bid</u>
612	IFC	<u>Industry Foundation Classes</u>
613	IFC	<u>Information For Construction</u>
614	IFD	<u>International Framework for Dictionaries (Library)</u>
615	IFMA	<u>International Facilities Management Association</u>
616	IFoA	<u>Integrated Form of Agreement</u>
617	IG	<u>Irish Grid</u>
618	IGES	<u>International Graphics Exchange Standard</u>
619	IGLC	<u>International Group of Learn Construction</u>
620	IIoT	<u>Industrial Internet of Things</u>
621	IIRA	<u>Industrial Internet Reference Architecture</u>
622	ILCD	<u>Integrated Life Cycle Design</u>
623	ILCD	<u>International Reference Life Cycle Data System</u>
624	IM	<u>Information Model/Modelling</u>
625	IMAN	<u>Inventario y Mantenimiento</u>
626	IMM	<u>Information Mirroring Model</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

627	IMO	<u>International Meteorological Organization</u>
628	IMP	<u>Information Management Process</u>
629	IMU	<u>Inertial Measurement Unit</u>
630	INE	<u>Instituto Nacional de Estadística (Spain)</u>
631	INSEE	<u>Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques</u>
632	IOT	<u>Internet of Things</u>
633	IOT HUB	<u>Internet of Things -</u>
634	IP	<u>Intellectual Property</u>
635	IP	<u>Internet Protocol</u>
636	IPC	<u>Integrated Project Coordinator</u>
637	IPCC	<u>Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change</u>
638	IPD	<u>Integrated Project Delivery</u>
639	IPI	<u>Integrated Project Insurance</u>
640	iPIM	iPIM is a building portfolio and asset management tool for the visualisation of key performance indicators and data.
641	IPLV	<u>Integrated Part Load Value</u>
642	IPMVP	<u>International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol</u>
643	IPP	<u>Initial Project Proposals</u>
644	IPP	<u>Inspection Point Program</u>
645	IPR	<u>Intellectual Property Rights</u>
646	iPredict	<u>Intelligent Prediction</u>
647	IR	<u>Information Requirements</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

648	IR	<u>Infrared</u>
649	IRMP	<u>Integrated Risk Management Plan</u>
650	IRR	<u>Internal Rate of Return</u>
651	IS	<u>International Standard</u>
652	iSCAN	<u>Intelligent Control and Analysis</u>
653	ISE	<u>The Institution of Structural Engineers</u>
654	ISES	<u>Intelligent Services For Energy-Efficient Design and Life Cycle Simulation</u>
655	ISG	<u>Implementation Support Group (Building Smart)</u>
656	ISI	<u>Information Sciences Institute</u>
657	ISIC	<u>International Standard Industrial Classification</u>
658	ISO	<u>International Standards Organisation</u>
659	ISS	<u>International Space Station</u>
660	ISV	<u>Independent Software Vendor</u>
661	IT	<u>Information Technology</u>
662	ITeC	<u>Institut de Tecnologia de la Construcció de Catalunya</u>
663	ITIL	<u>Information Technology Infrastructure Library</u>
664	ITSM	<u>IT Service Management</u>
665	ITU	<u>International Telecommunication Union</u>
666	IUK	<u>Infrastructure UK</u>
667	IVN	<u>Intelligent Virtual Network</u>
668	IWBI	<u>International Well Building Institute</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

669	IWMS	<u>Integrated Workplace Management System</u>
670	JCT	<u>Joint Contract Tribunal</u>
671	JIB	<u>Joint Industry Board</u>
672	JIT	<u>Just in Time</u>
673	JRC	<u>Joint Research Centre</u>
674	JSON	<u>JavaScript Object Notation</u>
675	JSON-LD	<u>JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data</u>
676	JV	<u>Joint Venture</u>
677	KER	<u>Key Exploitable Results</u>
678	KET	<u>Key Enabling Technologies</u>
679	KMS	<u>Knowledge Management System</u>
680	KNX	<u>Konnex</u>
681	KoM	<u>Kick-off Meeting</u>
682	KOS	<u>Knowledge Organization Systems</u>
683	KPI	<u>Key Performance Indicator</u>
684	KRS	<u>Knowledge Representation Systems</u>
685	L3P	<u>Linked Third Party</u>
686	LADAR	<u>Laser Detection and Ranging</u>
687	LAM	<u>Laser Aided Modelling</u>
688	LAN	<u>Local Area Network</u>
689	LAS	<u>Look-ahead Schedule</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

690	LBC	<u>Lean BIM Construction</u>
691	LBD	<u>Linked Building Data</u>
692	LC	<u>Lean Construction</u>
693	LCA	<u>Life Cycle Assessment</u>
694	LCC	<u>Life Cycle Contract</u>
695	LCC	<u>Life Cycle Cost</u>
696	LCCA	<u>Life-Cycle Cost Analysis</u>
697	LCCCA	<u>Life Cycle Cost Concrete Assessment</u>
698	LCD	<u>Liquid Crystal Display</u>
699	LCDN	<u>Life Cycle Data Network</u>
700	LCI	<u>Lean Construction Institute</u>
701	LCI	<u>Life Cycle Inventory</u>
702	LCIA	<u>Life Cycle Impact Assessment</u>
703	LCIE	<u>Life Cycle Information Exchange</u>
704	LCR	<u>Life Cycle Repairs /Replacement (Renewal)</u>
705	LCS	<u>Location Coding System (London Underground)</u>
706	LCT	<u>Life Cycle Tower</u>
707	LD	<u>Linked Data</u>
708	LDAC	<u>Linked Data in Architecture and Construction</u>
709	LE	<u>Large Enterprise</u>
710	LEAR	<u>Legal Entity Appointed Representative</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

711	LEC	<u>Local Energy Community</u>
712	LED	<u>Light Emitting Diode</u>
713	LEED	<u>Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design</u>
714	LHC	<u>Large Hadron Collider</u>
715	LIDAR	<u>Light Detection and ranging</u>
716	LIPS	<u>Lean in Public Sector</u>
717	Ln	<u>Linkedin</u>
718	LOD	<u>Level of model Detail</u>
719	LOD	<u>Level of Definition</u>
720	LOD	<u>Linked Open Data</u>
721	LOI	<u>Level of model Information</u>
722	LOIN	<u>Level of Information Need</u>
723	Lo-Ra	<u>Long Range</u>
724	LPD	<u>Lean Project Delivery</u>
725	LPDS	<u>Lean Project Delivery System</u>
726	LPN	<u>Low Power Network</u>
727	LPS	<u>Last Planner System</u>
728	LPT	<u>Lean Production Theory</u>
729	LPWA	<u>Low Power Wide Area</u>
730	LPWAN	<u>Low Power Wide Area Network</u>
731	LRM	<u>Last Responsible Moment</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

732	LRM	<u>Linear Referencing Method</u>
733	LRS	<u>Linear Referencing System</u>
734	LTOs	<u>Long-Term Objectives</u>
735	LTP	<u>Linked Third Party</u>
736	LU	<u>London Underground</u>
737	LV	<u>Low Voltage</u>
738	LZC	<u>Low to Zero Carbon</u>
739	M&E	<u>Mechanical and Electrical</u>
740	M&O	<u>Maintenance and Operation</u>
741	M&V	<u>Measurement and Verification</u>
742	M2M	<u>Machine-to-Machine</u>
743	MAE	<u>Mean Absolute Error</u>
744	MAPD	<u>Mean Absolute Percentage Deviation</u>
745	MAPE	<u>Mean Absolute Percentage Error</u>
746	MBCC	<u>Master Builders Construction Chemicals</u>
747	MBD	<u>Multi-Body Dynamics</u>
748	MBE	<u>Mean Bias Error</u>
749	MBR	<u>Membrane Bioreactor</u>
750	MBS	<u>Master Builders Solutions</u>
751	MBSD	<u>See MBS</u>
752	MC	<u>Main Contractor</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

753	MCIA	<u>Material Cost Impact Analysis</u>
754	MDS	<u>Manufacturing Digital Shadow</u>
755	MDT	<u>Manufacturing Digital Twin</u>
756	MEET	<u>Metered Energy Efficiency Transaction</u>
757	MEP	<u>Mechanical, Electrical, Plumbing</u>
758	MER	<u>Materials for Energy Recovery</u>
759	MES	<u>Manufacturing Execution System</u>
760	MET	<u>Metabolic Equivalent of Task</u>
761	MET	<u>Middle European Time</u>
762	MFA	<u>Material Flow Analysis</u>
763	MFA	<u>Material Footprint Assessment</u>
764	MFR	<u>Materials For Recycling</u>
765	MIDI	<u>Master Information Delivery Index</u>
766	MIDP	<u>Master Information Delivery Plan</u>
767	MIL	<u>Model in the Loop</u>
768	MIPS	<u>Material Input per Unit of Service</u>
769	ML	<u>Machine Learning</u>
770	MLB	<u>Mouse Left Button</u>
771	MLP	<u>Machine Learning Perceptron</u>
772	MLVS	<u>Main Low-Voltage Switchboard</u>
773	MMHW	<u>Method of Measurement for Highway Works (Highway Agency)</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

774	ModSCO	<u>Model -Supported Control</u>
775	MOPU	<u>Ministerio de Obras Públicas y Urbanismo (Spain)</u>
776	MP	<u>Management Plan</u>
777	MPA	<u>Multi-Party Agreement</u>
778	MPC	<u>Model Predictive Control</u>
779	MPDS	<u>Multi-Purpose Dynamic Simulator</u>
780	MPDT	<u>Model Production and Delivery Table</u>
781	MPM	<u>Manufacturing Process Management</u>
782	MQC	<u>Model Quality Control</u>
783	MQTT	<u>Message Queuing Telemetry Transport</u>
784	MR	<u>Mixed Reality</u>
785	MRB	<u>Mouse Right Button</u>
786	MRT	<u>Mean Radiant Temperature</u>
787	MSD	<u>Manpower Sources Diagram</u>
788	MSD	<u>Mean Square Deviation</u>
789	MSE	<u>Mean Square Error</u>
790	MSG	<u>Model Support Group (Building Smart)</u>
791	MSM	<u>Mirrored Spaces Model</u>
792	MTBF	<u>Mean Time Between Failures</u>
793	MTOE	<u>Million Tons of Oil Equivalent</u>
794	MTTF	<u>Mean Time to Failure</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

795	MTTR	<u>Mean Time to Resolution (Recovery, Repair)</u>
796	MVD	<u>Model View Definition</u>
797	MVP	<u>Market validation Program</u>
798	MVP	<u>Minimum Viable Product</u>
799	MWI	<u>Municipal Waste Incinerators</u>
800	N3	<u>Notation 3</u>
801	N3Logic	<u>Notation 3 Logic</u>
802	NaaS	<u>Native as a Service</u>
803	NACE	<u>Nomenclature statistique des Activités économiques dans la Communauté Européenne</u>
804	NACUBO	<u>National Association of College and University Business Officers</u>
805	NaN	<u>Not a Number</u>
806	NAO	<u>National Audit Office</u>
807	NASA	<u>National Aeronautics and Space Administration</u>
808	NBE	<u>Norma Básica de Edificación (Spain)</u>
809	NBI	<u>Northbound Interfaces</u>
810	NBIMS	<u>National BIM Standard (US)</u>
811	NB-IoT	<u>Narrow Band-Internet of Things</u>
812	NBS	<u>National Building Specification</u>
813	NBS	<u>National Bureau of Standards</u>
814	NC	<u>Numerical Control</u>
815	NCM	<u>National Calculation Methodology</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

816	NDA	<u>Non-Disclosure Agreement</u>
817	NDEA	<u>Non-Domestic Energy Assessment</u>
818	NDT	<u>National Digital Twin</u>
819	NEC	<u>New Engineering Contracts</u>
820	NEC3	<u>New Engineering Contract (3rd Iteration of the NEC contract)</u>
821	NEEDS	<u>New Energy Externalities Development for Sustainability</u>
822	NEN	<u>Nederlandse Norm</u>
823	NEX	<u>NEANEX</u>
824	NF	<u>National Framework</u>
825	NHS	<u>National Health Service</u>
826	NHWD	<u>Non Hazardous Waste Dispose</u>
827	NIA	<u>Net Internal Area</u>
828	NIBS	<u>National Institute of Building Sciences (US)</u>
829	NIEM	<u>National Information Exchange Model</u>
830	NIF's	<u>National Interoperability Frameworks</u>
831	NIST	<u>National Institute of Standards and Technology (US)</u>
832	NLP	<u>Natural Language Processing</u>
833	NLTK	<u>Natural Language Toolkit</u>
834	NMS	<u>National Master Specification</u>
835	NOK	<u>Not Okay</u>
836	NPC	<u>Net Present Cost</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

837	NPV	<u>Net Present Value</u>
838	NRM	<u>New Rules of Measurement</u>
839	NRM2	<u>New Rules of Measurement-2</u>
840	NRSF	<u>Non-Renewable Secondary Fuels</u>
841	NS	<u>Net Savings</u>
842	NSB	<u>National Standards Body</u>
843	NSSDC	<u>National Space Science Data Center</u>
844	NSSDCA	<u>NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Archive</u>
845	NST	<u>Negotiated Select Team</u>
846	NUIG	<u>National University of Ireland, Galway</u>
847	NURBS	<u>Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline Surfaces</u>
848	NZEB	<u>Near Zero Energy Buildings</u>
849	O&M	<u>Operations and Maintenance</u>
850	OA	<u>Open Access</u>
851	OASIS	<u>Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards</u>
852	OBDA	<u>Ontology-Based Data Access</u>
853	oBIX	<u>Open Building Information Xchange</u>
854	OBS	<u>Organisation Breakdown Structures</u>
855	OCC	<u>Occupant-centric Controls</u>
856	OCCS	<u>OmniClass Construction Classification System</u>
857	OCDE	<u>Organisation de Coopération et de Développement Économiques</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

858	OCE	<u>Order of Cost Estimates</u>
859	OCI	<u>Optimised Contractor Involvement</u>
860	OCIP	<u>Owner Controller Insurance Program</u>
861	OCX	<u>OLE Control EXtension</u>
862	ODA	<u>Olympic Delivery Authority</u>
863	ODP	<u>Ozone Depletion Potential</u>
864	OECD	<u>Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development</u>
865	OEE	<u>Overall Equipment Effectiveness</u>
866	OEF	<u>Organisational Environmental Footprint</u>
867	OEM	<u>Original Equipment Manufacturer</u>
868	OGC	<u>Office of Government Commerce</u>
869	OGC	<u>Open Geospatial Consortium</u>
870	ÖGNI	<u>Österreichische Gesellschaft für Nachhaltige Immobilienwirtschaft</u>
871	OHLE	<u>Overhead Line Electrification</u>
872	OIR	<u>Organization Information Requirement</u>
873	OLE	<u>Object Linking & Embedding</u>
874	OLE	<u>Overhead Line Electrification</u>
875	OMG	<u>Ontology for Managing Geometry</u>
876	OMSI	<u>Operations and Maintenance Support</u>
877	OOP	<u>Objective Oriented Production</u>
878	OPA	<u>Organizational Process Assets</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

879	OPC	<u>Object Linking and Embedding for Process Control</u>
880	OPC UA	<u>OPC Unified Architecture</u>
881	OPex	<u>Operating Expenses</u>
882	OPex	<u>Operational Expenditures</u>
883	OPM	<u>Ofek Property Management</u>
884	OPS	<u>Outline Procurement Strategy</u>
885	OPT	<u>Online Planning Tool</u>
886	OPY	<u>Octopussy Agence pour la création et la diffusion d'activités culturelles artistiques technologiques et Scientifiques</u>
887	OR	<u>Operational Rating</u>
888	ORD	<u>Open Research Data</u>
889	OS	<u>Ordnance Survey</u>
890	OTL	<u>Object Type Library</u>
891	OWA	<u>Open World Assumption</u>
892	OWL	<u>Ontology Web Language</u>
893	P&ID	<u>Piping and Instrumentation Diagrams</u>
894	P3	<u>P3 (Public Private Partnership)</u>
895	PaaS	<u>Platform as a Service</u>
896	PACE	<u>Property Advisers to the Civil Estate</u>
897	PAM	<u>Property Asset Management</u>
898	PARL	<u>Percentage Asset Remaining Life</u>
899	PaRS	<u>Pilot-Activated Recovery System</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

900	PAS	<u>Publically Available Specification</u>
901	PBX	<u>Private Branch Exchange</u>
902	PC	<u>Personal Computer</u>
903	PCI	<u>Pre-Construction Information</u>
904	PCI	<u>Payment Card Industry</u>
905	PC Price	<u>Prime Cost Price</u>
906	PCR	<u>Product Category Rules</u>
907	PC Sum	<u>Prime Cost Sum</u>
908	PD	<u>Predicted Desirable</u>
909	PDCA	<u>Plan – Do – Check – Adjust</u>
910	PDF	<u>Portable Document Format</u>
911	PdM	<u>Predictive Maintenance</u>
912	PDM	<u>Project Delivery Manager</u>
913	PDP	<u>Project Definition Plan</u>
914	PDSM	<u>Project Driven Scope Management</u>
915	PDT	<u>Product Data Templates</u>
916	PE	<u>Primary Energy Content (Use of)</u>
917	PEB	<u>Positive Energy Block/District</u>
918	PEB	<u>Proyectos de Ejecución BIM</u>
919	PEF	<u>Product Environmental Footprint</u>
920	PENR	<u>Primary Energy Non-Renewable Resources (Use of)</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

921	PENRE	<u>Primary Energy Non-Renewable, Energy Resources (Use of)</u>
922	PENRM	<u>Primary Energy Non-Renewable Resources used as raw materials (Use of)</u>
923	PENRT	<u>Primary Energy Non-Renewable, Energy Resources (Total Use)</u>
924	PEOU	<u>Perceived Ease-of-Use</u>
925	PEP	<u>Project Execution Plan</u>
926	PER	<u>Primary Energy Content of all Renewable Resources (Use of)</u>
927	PERE	<u>Use of renewable primary energy (Use of)</u>
928	PERM	<u>Renewable Primary Energy resources used as Raw Materials (Use of)</u>
929	PERT	<u>Renewable Primary Energy Resources (Use of)</u>
930	PESTEL or PESTLE	<u>Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental analysis</u>
931	PFD	<u>Process Flow Diagram</u>
932	PFI	<u>Private Finance Initiative</u>
933	PHP	<u>Hypertext Pre-processor</u>
934	PIB	<u>Planned Inspection of Buildings</u>
935	PID	<u>Proportional, Integral, and Derivative</u>
936	PII	<u>Professional Indemnity Insurance</u>
937	PIM	<u>Project Information Model</u>
938	PIN	<u>Prior Information/Indicative Notice</u>
939	PIP	<u>Project Implementation Plan</u>
940	PIR	<u>Passive InfraRed</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

941	PIR	<u>Project Information Requirement</u>
942	PIT	<u>Project Implementation Team</u>
943	PIX	<u>Project Information Exchange</u>
944	PLC	<u>Power Line Communication</u>
945	PLC	<u>Product Life Cycle</u>
946	PLC	<u>Programmable Logic Controllers</u>
947	PLM	<u>Product Lifecycle Management</u>
948	PM	<u>Person Month</u>
949	PM	<u>Portfolio Manager</u>
950	PM	<u>Project Management/Manager</u>
951	PM	<u>Property Management/Manager</u>
952	PMB	<u>Protocolo de Modelos BIM</u>
953	PMI	<u>Project Management Institute</u>
954	PMO	<u>Project Management Office</u>
955	PMO	<u>Product Modelling Ontology</u>
956	PMT	<u>Project Management Team</u>
957	PMV	<u>Predicted Mean Vote</u>
958	PO	<u>Policy Officer</u>
959	PO	<u>Project Officer</u>
960	POC	<u>Proof of Concept</u>
961	POCP	<u>Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

962	POE	<u>Post Occupancy Evaluation</u>
963	POS	<u>Proof of Stake</u>
964	POW	<u>Proof of Work</u>
965	PP	<u>Phases Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
966	PPA	<u>Power Purchase Agreement</u>
967	PPC	<u>Project Partnering Contracts</u>
968	PPC	<u>Percent Plan Complete</u>
969	PPD	<u>Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied</u>
970	PPDP	<u>Privacy-Preserving Data Publishing</u>
971	PPM	<u>Planned Preventive Maintenance</u>
972	PPML	<u>Privacy Preserving Machine Learning</u>
973	PPP	<u>Public Private Partnership</u>
974	PQQ	<u>Pre-Qualification Questionnaire</u>
975	Pr	<u>Products Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
976	PSCD	<u>Public Sector Construction Database</u>
977	PSRL	<u>Product Semantics Representation Language</u>
978	PTEC	<u>Plataforma Tecnológica Española de Construcción</u>
979	PU	<u>Predicted Undesirable</u>
980	PU	<u>Perceived Usefulness</u>
981	P&ID	<u>Piping and Instrumentation Diagram</u>
982	P&CM	<u>Project and Construction Management</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

983	PV	<u>Photovoltaics</u>
984	PV	<u>Present Value</u>
985	PV	<u>Process Variable</u>
986	PVGIS	<u>Photovoltaic Geographical Information System</u>
987	Q&A	<u>Questions and Answers</u>
988	QA	<u>Quality Assurance</u>
989	QC	<u>Quality Control</u>
990	QFD	<u>Quality Function Deployment</u>
991	QL	<u>Quality Level</u>
992	QoS	<u>Quality of Service</u>
993	QoS	<u>Quality of Signal</u>
994	QR	<u>Quick Response</u>
995	QS	<u>Quantity Surveyor</u>
996	QTO	<u>Quantity Take Off</u>
997	QUDT	<u>Quantity, Unit, Dimension and Type</u>
998	R&M	<u>Renovation & Modernization</u>
999	R&D	<u>Research and Development</u>
1000	R2M	<u>Research to Market</u>
1001	R2RML	<u>RDB to RDF Mapping Language</u>
1002	RACI	<u>Responsible, Accountable, Consulted and Informed</u>
1003	RAD	<u>Rapid Application Development</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1004	RAG	<u>Red, Amber, Green</u>
1005	RAM	<u>Random Access Memory</u>
1006	RAMI	<u>Reference Architectural Model Industry</u>
1007	RBNN	<u>Radial Bias Neural Network</u>
1008	RCA	<u>Root Cause Analysis</u>
1009	RCM	<u>Reliability Centred Maintenance</u>
1010	RDF	<u>Resource Description Framework</u>
1011	RDFa	<u>Resource Description Framework in Attributes</u>
1012	RDFS	<u>RDF Schema</u>
1013	RDS	<u>Room Data Sheet</u>
1014	RDS	<u>Room Data Schedule</u>
1015	REST	<u>Representational State Transfer</u>
1016	RFI	<u>Request for Information</u>
1017	RFID	<u>Radio-Frequency IDentification</u>
1018	RFP	<u>Request for Proposal</u>
1019	RFQ	<u>Request for Quotation</u>
1020	RFT	<u>Request for Tender</u>
1021	RGB	<u>Red, Green, Blue</u>
1022	RIA	<u>Regulatory Impact Analysis</u>
1023	RIA	<u>Regulatory Impact Assessment</u>
1024	RIA	<u>Research and Innovation Actions</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1025	RIAS	<u>Royal Incorporation of Architects in Scotland</u>
1026	RIBA	<u>Royal Institute of British Architects</u>
1027	RICS	<u>Royal Institute of Chartered Surveyors</u>
1028	RIF	<u>Rule Interchange Format</u>
1029	RIT	<u>Room Integrity Testing</u>
1030	RMIT	<u>Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology</u>
1031	RMSE	<u>Root Mean Square Error</u>
1032	RobMos	<u>Reduced Order Building Model Simulation</u>
1033	ROI	<u>Return on Investment</u>
1034	ROM	<u>Read-only Memory</u>
1035	ROM	<u>Reduced Order Model</u>
1036	ROM	<u>Rough Order Model</u>
1037	RPI	<u>Retail Price Index</u>
1038	RSF	<u>Renewable Secondary Fuels (Use of)</u>
1039	RSL	<u>Reference Service Life</u>
1040	RSR	<u>Radioactive Substances Regulation</u>
1041	RST	<u>Rhetorical Structure Theory</u>
1042	RSVP	<u>Répondez, s'il Vous Plaît</u>
1043	RT	<u>Real Time</u>
1044	RTC	<u>Real Time Clock</u>
1045	RTD	<u>Research and Technological Development</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1046	RTF	<u>Rich Text Format</u>
1047	RTL	<u>Register Transfer Level</u>
1048	RTO	<u>Research Technology Organization</u>
1049	RTU	<u>Remote Terminal Unit</u>
1050	RUL	<u>Remaining Useful Life</u>
1051	RV	<u>Reference View</u>
1052	RVA	<u>Risk and Vulnerability Assessment</u>
1053	RWD	<u>Radioactive Waste Disposed</u>
1054	SA	<u>Site Area</u>
1055	SAL	<u>Security Aspect Letter</u>
1056	SaaS	<u>Software as a Service</u>
1057	SAM	<u>Serviceable Available Market</u>
1058	SAP	<u>Standard Assessment Procedure</u>
1059	SAP	<u>Systems, Applications, Products in Data Processing</u>
1060	SAREF	<u>Smart Appliance Reference</u>
1061	SBC	<u>Standard Building Tribunal</u>
1062	SBD	<u>Set-Based Design</u>
1063	SBEM	<u>Simplified Building Energy Model</u>
1064	SBI	<u>Southbound Interfaces</u>
1065	SBR	<u>Sequencing Batch Reactor</u>
1066	SBS	<u>Small Business Service</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1067	SCADA	<u>Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition</u>
1068	SCAS	<u>Smart, Connected Asset Systems</u>
1069	SCCS	<u>Supply Chain Capability Summary</u>
1070	SCM	<u>Smart Contracting Module</u>
1071	SCM	<u>Supply Chain Management</u>
1072	SCO	<u>Smart Connected Operations</u>
1073	SCoT	<u>Smart Connected Things</u>
1074	SCP	<u>Smart, Connected Products</u>
1075	SCPS	<u>Smart, Connected Product Systems</u>
1076	SDD	<u>System Design Description</u>
1077	SDGs	<u>Sustainable Development Goals</u>
1078	SDN	<u>Software-Defined Networking</u>
1079	SDNF	<u>Steel Detailing Neutral Format</u>
1080	SDO	<u>Standards Developing Organization</u>
1081	SDS	<u>Space Data Sheet</u>
1082	SDS	<u>Space Data Schedule</u>
1083	SECAP	<u>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan</u>
1084	SEER	<u>Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio</u>
1085	SEP	<u>Superior Energy Performance®</u>
1086	SETAC	<u>Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry</u>
1087	SEUs	<u>Significant Energy Uses</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1088	SFA	<u>Substance Flow Analysis</u>
1089	SFP	<u>Specific Fan Power</u>
1090	SGML	<u>Standard Generalized Markup Language</u>
1091	SGNI	<u>Schweizer Gesellschaft für Nachhaltige Immobilienwirtschaft</u>
1092	SHACL	<u>Shapes Constraint Language</u>
1093	SIA	<u>Security Industry Authority</u>
1094	SIL	<u>Safety Integrity Level</u>
1095	SIL	<u>Smithsonian Institution Libraries</u>
1096	SIL	<u>Software in the Loop</u>
1097	SIM	<u>Structural Information Model</u>
1098	SIR	<u>Savings to Investment Ratio</u>
1099	SKOS	<u>Simple Knowledge Organization System</u>
1100	SLA	<u>Service Level Agreement</u>
1101	SLCA	<u>Social Life Cycle Assessment</u>
1102	SM	<u>Secondary Materials</u>
1103	SME	<u>Small and Medium Enterprises</u>
1104	SMP	<u>Standard Method and Procedure</u>
1105	SMS	<u>Short Message Service</u>
1106	SMT	<u>Site Management Team</u>
1107	SMTP	<u>Simple Mail Transfer Protocol</u>
1108	SoA	<u>State of Art</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1109	SOA	<u>Service Oriented Architectures</u>
1110	SOAP	<u>Simple Object Access Protocol</u>
1111	SOM	<u>Serviceable Obtainable Market</u>
1112	SOSA	<u>Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator</u>
1113	SP	<u>Setpoint</u>
1114	Sp	<u>Spaces Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
1115	SPARQL	<u>Simple Protocol and RDF Query Language</u>
1116	SPE	<u>Single Purpose Entity</u>
1117	SPF	<u>STEP Physical File</u>
1118	SPFF	<u>STEP Physical File Format (IFC)</u>
1119	SPHERE	<u>Service Platform to Host and SharE REsidential data</u>
1120	SPie	<u>Specifiers' Properties information exchange</u>
1121	SPP	<u>Simple Payback Period</u>
1122	SQL	<u>Structured Query Language</u>
1123	SRI	<u>Smart Reading Indicators</u>
1124	SRT	<u>Smart Ready Technologies</u>
1125	Ss	<u>Systems Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
1126	SSL	<u>Structural Slab Level</u>
1127	SSL	<u>Secure Sockets Layer</u>
1128	SSN	<u>Semantic Sensor Network</u>
1129	SSO	<u>Single Sign-On</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1130	STEP	<u>STandard for Exchange of Product Model Data</u>
1131	STL	<u>Standard Tessellation Language</u>
1132	STOs	<u>Short-Term Objectives</u>
1133	SUS	<u>Software Update Services</u>
1134	SUS	<u>System Usability Scale</u>
1135	SVM	<u>Support Vector Machine</u>
1136	SWOP	<u>Semantic Web-based Open engineering Platform</u>
1137	SWOT	<u>Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat</u>
1138	SWRL	<u>Semantic Web Rule Language</u>
1139	TA	<u>Technical Advisor</u>
1140	TAI	<u>Teaching as Inquiring</u>
1141	TAM	<u>Technology Acceptance Model</u>
1142	TAM	<u>Total Addressable Market</u>
1143	TBC	<u>To Be Confirmed</u>
1144	TBD	<u>To Be Determined, Decided or Defined</u>
1145	TBM	<u>Technical Building Management</u>
1146	TBM	<u>Temporary Benchmark</u>
1147	TBM	<u>Tunnel Boring Machine</u>
1148	TCP	<u>Transmission Control Protocol</u>
1149	TCQ	<u>Temps, Cost, Qualitat (Catalan)</u>
1150	TEAC	<u>Thermal Energy Anomalous Consumption</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1151	TED	<u>Tenders Electronic Daily</u>
1152	TEFMA	<u>Tertiary Education Facilities Management Association</u>
1153	TER	<u>Target Emission Rate</u>
1154	TFEE	<u>Target Fabric Energy Efficiency</u>
1155	TIC	<u>Tecnologías de la Información y de la Comunicación (Spanish)</u>
1156	TIDP	<u>Task Information Delivery Plan</u>
1157	TILT	<u>Transfer Implementation Leadership Team</u>
1158	TL	<u>Tube Lines</u>
1159	TLS	<u>Terrestrial Laser Scanner</u>
1160	TLS	<u>Transport Layer Security</u>
1161	TMY	<u>Typical Meteorological Year</u>
1162	TNO	<u>Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek</u>
1163	TOC	<u>Table of Contents</u>
1164	TOE	<u>Technology-Organisation-Environment</u>
1165	TOE	<u>Tonne of Oil Equivalent</u>
1166	TOID	<u>Topographic Identifier</u>
1167	TPI	<u>Tender Price Index</u>
1168	TPS	<u>Toyota Production System</u>
1169	TPS	<u>Transient Protection System</u>
1170	TRL	<u>Technological Readiness Level</u>
1171	TS	<u>Thermal Sensation</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1172	TSA	<u>Time Stamp Authority (Secure Time Stamp Authority)</u>
1173	TSI	<u>Thermal Sensation Index</u>
1174	TTF	<u>Task Technology Fit (model)</u>
1175	TUI	<u>Tangible User Interface</u>
1176	TVD	<u>Target Value Delivery</u>
1177	TVD	<u>Target Value Design</u>
1178	TVP	<u>Target Value Production</u>
1179	UC	<u>Use Case</u>
1180	UCD	<u>User Centred Design</u>
1181	UCL	<u>University College London</u>
1182	UD	<u>Unpredicted Desirable</u>
1183	UFA	<u>Usable Floor Area</u>
1184	UI	<u>User Interface</u>
1185	UID	<u>Unique Identifier</u>
1186	UK	<u>United Kingdom</u>
1187	Umbel	<u>Upper Mapping and Binding Exchange Layer</u>
1188	UML	<u>Unified Model/ling Language</u>
1189	UMUX	<u>Usability Metric for UX (User Experience)</u>
1190	UN	<u>United Nations</u>
1191	UNDP	<u>United Nations Development Programme</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1192	UNE	<u>Una Norma Española</u>
1193	UNEP	<u>United Nations Environment Programme</u>
1194	UNGA	<u>United Nations General Assembly</u>
1195	Uniclass	<u>Unified Classification System</u>
1196	UoM	<u>Units of Measure</u>
1197	UPRN	<u>Unique Property Reference Number</u>
1198	UPS	<u>Uninterruptible Power Supplies</u>
1199	URI	<u>Unique Resource Identifier</u>
1200	URI	<u>Uniform Resource Identifiers</u>
1201	URL	<u>Uniform Resource Locator</u>
1202	URN	<u>Uniform Resource Name</u>
1203	US (USA)	<u>United States (of America)</u>
1204	USACE	<u>United States Army Corps of Engineers</u>
1205	USC	<u>University of Southern California</u>
1206	USGBC	<u>United States Green Building Council</u>
1207	UTC	<u>Coordinated Universal Time</u>
1208	UX	<u>User Experience</u>
1209	UXB	<u>Unexploded Bomb</u>
1210	UU	<u>Unpredicted Undesirable</u>
1211	UUID	<u>Universally Unique Identifier</u>
1212	V2B	<u>Vehicle to Building</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1213	V2G	<u>Vehicle to Grid</u>
1214	VB (VBM)	<u>Virtual Building (Model)</u>
1215	vBDTA	<u>Vertical Building Digital Twin Aggregate</u>
1216	VC	<u>Video Conference</u>
1217	VC	<u>Virtual Call</u>
1218	VC	<u>Virtual Construction</u>
1219	VCMP	<u>Virtual Construction Management Platform</u>
1220	VDC	<u>Virtual Design and Construction</u>
1221	VDR	<u>Virtual Data Room</u>
1222	VE	<u>Virtual Environmental</u>
1223	V-ECU	<u>Virtual Electronic Control Units</u>
1224	VEL	<u>Virtual Energy Lab</u>
1225	VEM	<u>Virtual Energy Manager</u>
1226	VERDE	<u>Valoración de Eficiencia de Referencia de Edificios</u>
1227	VFM	<u>Value for Money</u>
1228	VOC	<u>Volatile Organic Compounds</u>
1229	VoIP	<u>Voice over Internet Protocol</u>
1230	VPN	<u>Virtual Private Network</u>
1231	VPP	<u>Virtual Power Plant</u>
1232	VR	<u>Virtual Reality</u>
1233	VRML	<u>Virtual Reality Modelling Language</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1234	VSM	<u>Value Stream Mapping</u>
1235	VT	<u>Virtual Twin</u>
1236	VTT	<u>VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd</u>
1237	W3C	<u>World Wide Web Consortium</u>
1138	WAF	<u>Web Application Firewall</u>
1239	WAN	<u>Wide Area Network</u>
1240	WB	<u>Wet Bulb</u>
1241	WBDG	<u>Whole Building Design Guide</u>
1242	WBI	<u>Well Building Institute</u>
1243	WBS	<u>Work Breakdown Structure</u>
1244	WBT	<u>Wet Bulb Temperature</u>
1245	WGBC	<u>World Green Building Council</u>
1246	WGR	<u>Waste Generation Rate</u>
1247	WIP	<u>Work-in-Process</u>
1248	WLC	<u>Whole Life Costing</u>
1249	WMO	<u>World Meteorological Organization</u>
1250	WO	<u>Work Order</u>
1251	WP	<u>Work Package</u>
1252	WR	<u>Work Results Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
1253	WRAP	<u>Waste & Resources Action Programme</u>
1254	WRL	<u>Vrml World</u>

This project has received funding from the H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805

SPHERE
BIM DIGITAL TWIN PLATFORM

1255	WS	<u>Work Results for Specifications (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>
1256	WTO	<u>World Trade Organization</u>
1257	WWP	<u>Weekly Work Plan</u>
1258	WWW	<u>World Wide Web</u>
1259	XML	<u>eXtensible Markup Language</u>
1260	XR	<u>Extended Reality</u>
1261	X-REF	<u>Cross Reference</u>
1262	XSD	<u>XML Schema Definition</u>
1263	XSLT	<u>eXtensible Stylesheet Language Transformations</u>
1264	XSP	<u>Cross Section Positions</u>
1265	XSS	<u>Cross-Site Scripting</u>
1266	XWiki	<u>XWiki</u>
1267	Zz	<u>CAD Table (CPIC Uniclass 2)</u>